

SITE GS/S	DATE 6/23-24/79	AREA NE	SQUARE R2	PAGE
 Feature No.	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top: 10.72	Bottom: 10.71 - 10.70
	DIMENSIONS			
Diameter: 60 cm	Width: 43 to R2 Balk	Length:	Depth: 1 cm - 2.2 cm	

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions
1	GYPSUM	OFF WHITE - BUFF	VERY HARD	PACKED Grainy	T	Lm ← 1 small nat * Gp Gr Char Flecks ← Do Ba
					D	Al Other
					T	Lm Gp Gr Char Do
					D	Ba Al Other
					T	Lm Gp Gr Char Do
					D	Ba Al Other
					T	Lm Gp Gr Char Do
					D	Ba Al Other
					T	Lm Gp Gr Char Do
					D	Ba Al Other

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/ CI No./ 15	B&W: Roll/ BW1 No./ 15
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DRAWN	Area Plan: Plotted 1:50	Feature Plan:	Sections: (GS79) In R2 Balk Section
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: Significance: If result of levelling floor - means was finish work on floor up to where quarry work ended (ledge forming W side R2). Also - finishwork covered by tentatively O.K. Working Rubble left abandoned - (S) R2.

* Patch not completely cleared - one quarter section and strip along R2 Balk
GYPSUM FILL SAMPLED Inorganic No. 1